

RESPONSE PAPER

LAST NAME: LAWAL

FIRST NAME: ISMAIL

PROGRAM CODE: DIPH

COURSE CODE: ACA-401D

PERIOD NUMBER: 1

INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA

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The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)
 The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:
 The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)
 The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)
 My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%
 The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Writing a good academic essay (EUCLID 2024, 7-9)
2. Punctuation (EUCLID 2024, 7-9)
3. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2024, 33- 36)
4. Some rules of thumb for writing papers (EUCLID 2024, 8- 12)
5. American Vs. British English (EUCLID 2024, 24- 31)

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INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC WRITING (DOCTORATE)

1) INTRODUCTION

I have tried to familiarize myself with the course, even though I am initially nervous and confused about how to go about this as this is my first attempt. The basic concepts I was able to learn from this course are highlighted below. EUCLID University's courses ACA-401D focus on enhancing students' academic writing skills, tailored to master's and Doctoral levels, respectively. The objective of the course is to equip students with the proficiency required to produce scholarly papers that meet international academic and professional standards. In this response paper, I will highlight most of the key areas discussed as a rule of thumb in writing internationally acceptable papers.

2) WRITING GOOD ACADEMIC ESSAY

This course provides a comprehensive review of proper English writing fundamentals. It emphasizes the distinctions between U.S. and U.K. English, including

spelling and punctuation use. Students are trained to place commas correctly, avoid plagiarism, and structure papers with logical coherence. The course also familiarizes students with the Chicago/Turabian manual of style, ensuring adherence to accepted academic guidelines. Proficiency in tools like Zotero and Grammarly education to be installed for use in references and document development.

a) PLAGIARISM

This section was designed for doctoral candidates. It discussed academic writing intricacies more deeply, focusing on producing publishable-grade scholarly papers. Plagiarism avoidance and maintaining logical flow in writing. Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information. Plagiarism comes in two forms, both unacceptable. First, you plagiarize when you use the words of a source without quotation marks. If you take words from a source, you must use quotation marks, not just a footnote. Moreover, you should not present a close paraphrase from a source: either use the exact words with quotation marks or restate the point in your own words. Additionally, students review doctoral theses from leading universities and engage with texts specifically addressing doctoral dissertations. This ensures that their writing meets the rigorous standards expected at the Ph.D. Level. To avoid plagiarism, the solution is to properly CITE the author or source that has provided the information one is using (EUCLID 2021, 6).

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b) OTHER RULES OF THUMB FOR WRITING PAPER

The course highlighted many cheat sheets to be used in writing excellent papers: this starts with a proper style guide with consistency, punctuation, use of quotes, and where not to use quotes. How to quote and reference systems. Many students entering master's and doctoral programs struggle with academic writing due to differences in writing styles across disciplines and cultures. The course addresses these challenges by teaching internationally accepted standards of academic writing. With the use of citation management tools like Zotero, students can efficiently handle references, ensuring proper attribution and avoiding plagiarism. These tools are essential for writing research papers, especially at the doctoral level. This course discusses some methods for critical thinking to train students to develop arguments systematically, ensuring coherence between ideas, which is vital for thesis and dissertation writing.

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i) PUNCTUATION

This section explains the use of various punctuation styles like the use of a pair of commas to surround a non-defining clause (one which adds descriptive information but which can be removed without losing the meaning of the sentence) – note that only ‘which’ or ‘who’ can be used in this type of clause, not ‘that. They use Bullet points, colon and semi-colon, Dashe and Hyphens, etc. This also helps distinguish between US and UK English.

3) CONCLUSION

Euclid University's ACA-401D courses provide a comprehensive approach to academic writing. By emphasizing proper English usage, logical structure, citation management, and plagiarism avoidance, these courses prepare students for success in their academic and professional careers and made me realize that I ~~still have a lot to learn in~~ English.

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REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.